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SYNTHESIZED HYDROXYAPATITE FROM SEASHELLS AS A SUSTAINABLE ADSORBENT FOR CR(VI) REMEDIATION

M.P.H. Perera*¹, H.M.S.K. Haputhenna¹, Gayan Amarasooriya¹, S.I. Ratnayake², Nimila Dushyantha¹

¹*Department of Applied Earth Sciences, Uva Wellassa University, Badulla, Sri Lanka*

²*Department of Science and Technology, Uva Wellassa University, Badulla, Sri Lanka*

**Corresponding Author E-mail: Pawaniperera1221@gmail.com*

Chromium is extensively used in various industrial processes, including metal plating, stainless steel manufacturing, and leather tanning. Due to the high toxicity of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)), it presents substantial hazards to human health and environmental ecosystems. The study investigates the removal of Cr(VI) ions from aqueous solutions using seashell-synthesized hydroxyapatite (SSHA) as a cost-effective adsorbent, addressing a gap in previous research. Cr(VI) removal was investigated by isotherm experiments and was analyzed with an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. The characteristics of SSHA were analyzed using Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray Diffraction (XRD) techniques. Other parameters, such as pH, adsorbent dosage, and contact time in relation to the initial Cr(VI) concentration, were systematically evaluated. Experimental results revealed that SSHA achieved a maximum removal efficiency of 39.51% at an optimal dose of 1 g, at pH 7, for an initial 10 mg/L Cr(VI) concentration with particle sizes ranging from 0.125 mm to 0.5 mm. Adsorption studies conducted across initial Cr(VI) concentrations of 5–25 mg/L (at pH 7.0 and 27°C) indicated that the adsorption behavior was better described by the Freundlich isotherm model, with correlation coefficients $R^2 = 0.9555$ and $R^2 = 0.8334$ for 5 mg/L and 25 mg/L, respectively. It suggests adsorption on a heterogeneous surface with possible multilayer formation. The Freundlich isotherm model constant (K_F) was found 7.406 mg/g and 7.702 mg/g, respectively, for initial 5 and 25 mg/L Cr(VI), while the Langmuir model yielded negative values for both 5 and 25 mg/L initial Cr(VI), indicating an unfavorable monolayer adsorption process. The FTIR and XRD analyses of Cr(VI)-adsorbed SSHA confirmed that Cr(VI) was not incorporated structurally within the hydroxyapatite lattice but was rather adsorbed onto the surface of SSHA.

Keywords: Seashells, Hydroxyapatite, Adsorption, Adsorption isotherm, Chromium removal